

Expanding the boundaries of compulsory citizenship behavior: Its impact on some organizational outputs

Sevda Ahmadian¹, Harun Sesen², Semih Soran³

¹ Faculty of Economics and Business, Girne American University, Cyprus (Northern)

² Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, European University of Lefke, Cyprus (Northern)

³ Faculty of Aviation and Aeronautical Science, Ozyegin University, Turkey

corresponding e-mail: [sevdaahmadian\[at\]gau\(dot\)edu\(dot\)tr](mailto:sevdaahmadian[at]gau(dot)edu(dot)tr)

address: University Drive 5, Karaoglanoglu, Girne, Via Mersin 10, Turkey

Abstract: Researches have mainly been focused on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) positive effects to organizations. On the other hand, Compulsory Citizenship Behavior (CCB) is a rather new subject in both national and international literature. Transformation of organizational citizenship behaviors, which are expected to have positive effects on the organizational success into CCB due to various administrative and social pressures, brings about numerous negative consequences for employees and the organization. But the quantity of studies conducted on this subject is very limited for the time being. In this framework, the main aim of this study is to contribute to literature by analyzing the dynamics of CCB in a different culture and different line of business.

In this study, relations between CCB and some positive and negative organizational attitudes and behaviors are examined. 635 people working in various accommodation businesses have participated in this research. Findings have shown that CCB is positively correlated with negative organizational consequences; and negatively correlated with positive organizational attitudes and behaviors. According to this, manager/supervisor related CCBs increase employees' intentions to quit work, their level of burnout, job stress, social loafing behaviors, and conflict with their colleagues; and decrease their innovative behaviors, identification with the organization, and individual oriented OCBs.

JEL Classifications: D20, D23, M12

Keywords: Compulsory citizenship behavior, intention to quit, burnout, job stress

Citation: Ahmadian, S., Sesen, H., Soran, S. (2017). Expanding the boundaries of compulsory citizenship behavior: Its impact on some organizational outputs. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 13(1), 110-118, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/beh.2017.08>

1. Introduction

For many years, the subject of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) has attracted interest from management and organization field. A number of studies on this subject have demonstrated that these behaviors produce numerous beneficial outputs for organizations without creating extra costs; and this situation increases the interest in the subject. OCB, which is characterized by voluntarism, altruism, loyalty and help (Organ, 1988) is considered as a fundamental behavior to improve performance, effectiveness and productivity of organizations (Podsakoff et al., 2000; Turnipseed & Murkison, 1996).

On the other hand, this viewpoint that has been developing over years has not taken into account the diversions from OCB; and ignored the negative side of it. However, some studies show that OCBs that are presented voluntarily in organizations, can be used as a tool for suppression by certain powerful people (e.g. the boss, colleagues. etc.). OCBs in this way have even become one of the job requirements by diverging from their voluntary basis (Bolino et al., 2004; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007). Compulsory citizenship behaviour (CCB), defined as employees' involuntary extra-role work activities that have positive effects to

the organization (Vigoda-Gadot, 2006), has long been over hooked; and its negative consequences greatly need to be discovered. In fact, CCB represents a much more negative reflection of extra-role behavior (Porpora, 1989).

Fundamental research question of this research is to explore whether compulsory citizenship behavior (CCB), which has transformed into an obligation by diverging from its voluntary basis (Vigoda-Gadot, 2006), has the negative impacts within organization on individuals' organizational attitudes and behaviors, such as intention to quit, burnout, innovativeness, job stress, job performance and social loafing. Latest research results show that that CCB negatively affects OCB via impairing organizational identification (Zaho et al., 2014).

2. Literature review

2.1 Organizational citizenship behavior

The concept of organizational behavior was the first used by Smith et al. (1983) and defined as "discretionary behaviors of organization employees that go beyond their formal roles such as helping others or supporting organization". Organ (1988) considers these behaviors as behaviors going beyond formal roles, which are not reviewed for reward and promotion processes and performed by individuals without expecting any rewards in return.

These behaviors are studied in various perspectives centered on performance, role behaviors or interpersonal behaviors. The organizational behavior is labeled with various concepts such as "organizational citizenship behaviors" or "good soldier syndrome" (Organ, 1988; Organ & Ryan, 1995; Turnipseed & Murkison, 2000), "positive social behaviors in work environment" (George, 1991), "organizational improvisation" (George & Brief, 1992), "extra-role behaviors" (Van Dyne & Lepine, 1998), "contextual performance" (Motowidlo & Van Scotter, 1994) or "pro-social organizational behavior" (Brief & Motowidlo, 1986). OCB might include positive behaviors going beyond formal roles, such as being sensitive in reacting to other people's mistakes, discussing problems with others, abiding by the deadlines and voluntarily helping others with their tasks (Kidwell et al., 1997; Podsakoff et al., 2000).

When the literature is reviewed, it can be concluded that researchers are not able to be in agreement on the dimensions of OCB. For instance, Podsakoff et al. (2000) defines more than 30 OCB dimensions in their literature review. Organ (1988), who made the first dimensioning studies on OCB, describes 5-dimensional description as altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, civic virtue and sportsmanship.

Many researchers have focused on the relationship of OCB and some organizational factors. In this regard, it is argued that OCB is in positive relationship with job satisfaction of employees (Bateman & Organ, 1983), their motivation (Rioux & Penner, 2001), organizational fairness of perception (Folger, 1993; Moorman, 1991), and performance of the organization (Podsakoff et al., 2000). It is stated that organizational success increases as OCBs of employees increase (Podsakoff et al., 2000), and OCBs help managers to use their time more effectively, increase coordination of activities, and support attracting successful individuals into the organization (Podsakoff et al., 1997).

As it can be seen, studies highlight the positive aspects of OCB and do not provide enough emphasis to the negative aspects of OCB. However, continuous emphasis on the positive aspects of OCB makes it a part of job definition over time and transforms it into a requirement, which signals about critical problem for the success of the organization.

2.2 Compulsory citizenship behavior

By questioning the border between the successes of the organization and having employees feel that they are obliged to work for the success of the organization, Vigoda-Gadot (2006) has introduced discussion of the concept of compulsory citizenship behavior. Vigoda-Gadot has stated that compelling behaviors of managers may negatively affect organizational behaviors and attitudes of employees such as job stress and burnout. Since the basis of OCB is the personal voluntary choice of the individual, Vigoda-Gadot claimed that compulsion cannot be considered as OCB, and brought up the concept of compulsory citizenship (Vigoda-Gadot, 2006).

Vigoda-Gadot shows that CCBs appear while employees are "... obliged to display extra role behaviors that involve volunteering in unofficial work environments due to strong social or managerial pressures" (Vigoda-Gadot, 2006). In other words, when the individual is obliged to display prosocial behaviors in the work environment, this can be named as CCB. In order to have CCB to happen, employees have to display positive behaviors beyond their roles (not in their job definition) (Vigoda-Gadot, 2007).

Certainly, it is not appropriate to consider all kinds of behaviors beyond employee's role as CCBs. If the employee is voluntarily undertaking the responsibilities of a colleague in their absence or voluntarily helping a colleague with a tough situation, this cannot be described as CCB. When the employee displays such beyond the role behaviors due to pressures from their supervisor or boss, or the employee feels obliged to display such behaviors, it can be referred as CCB. For example, it can be described as CCB when a supervisor or boss forces an employee to both train a new colleague and perform their own duties.

A manager or compulsory persuasion behaviors can be seen as the most fundamental premise of CCB (Vigoda-Gadot, 2006). A manager who behaves aggressively is defined as "the manager displaying hostile attitude through verbal or different behaviors without any physical contact" (Tepper, 2000, p. 178). It is found that such behaviors are displayed towards subordinates who cannot take the risk of losing the job or other negative consequences (Tepper et al., 2004). It is crucial to encourage OCB in the organization in order to create a positive working environment and ensure high effectiveness. However, communicating this intensely, putting pressures on the employee in some ways, transforms OCB into CCB.

In the research conducted on the outcomes of CCB, Vigoda-Gadot (2007) examined the relationship between CCBs of some Israeli teachers and some organizational outcomes such as job stress and job satisfaction. Most of the participants stated that they feel great pressure on themselves to display CCB. Findings of Vigoda-Gadot suggest that CCB might be much more common in the professional life than it is thought. It is found that there is positive correlation between CCB and job stress, organizational policy, intention to quit, and burnout; and negative correlation between CCB and innovativeness, job satisfaction, and job performance (Vigoda-Gadot, 2007). In this approach, the purpose of this study is to contribute to the developing literature by examining the dynamics of CCB in a different culture and different line of business.

2.3 Outcomes of CCB

Compulsory citizenship behavior is rather new subject in both national and international literature. Hence, the amount of studies conducted on this subject is very limited for the time being. The only applied research on this subject is conducted by Vigoda-Gadot (2007) with the group of teachers in Israel. It has been found that CCB is positively correlated with job stress, organizational policy, intention to quit, negligent behaviors, and burnout.

Meanwhile, CCB is found negatively correlated with innovativeness, job satisfaction, OCB, and duty performance.

This study explores relationship between CCB and both Vigoda-Gadot's (2007) and other variables.

Hypotheses that are developed in this framework are given below:

- Hypothesis 1: There is positive correlation between CCB and intention to leave work, burnout, job stress, social loafing behavior, and conflict between colleagues.
- Hypothesis 2: There is negative relationship between CCB and innovativeness, identification, OCB, and organizational trust.

3. Method

3.1 Participants

635 people working in various accommodation businesses have participated in this research. The ages of participants range from 18 to 63 years old ($Avr = 26.96$, and $sd = 7.73$); the duration of their employment ranges from 1 to 33 years ($Avr = 4.70$, and $sd = 5.65$). 36.2% of participants are women and 63.7% are men.

3.2 Measures

All measures were translated and adapted from English to Turkish. In the translation and adaptation process for the measures, a method based on a model described by Bristlin et al. (1973) was used, which consisted of five steps: forward translation, assessment of the forward translation, backward translation, assessment of the backward translation, and a discussion with experts.

In order to evaluate CCBs of participants, a 5-item scale from Vigoda-Gadot (2007) is used. Participants are asked to score to what extent they agree with expressions on a Likert scale (1 - I don't agree at all; 5 - I totally agree). The reliability coefficient of the scale (Cronbach alpha) is calculated as 0.94.

Intention to leave (4 items), burnout (6 items), innovation (6 items) and job stress (4 items) are measured with scales adapted from Vigoda-Gadot (2007)'s study. All the measures were 5 point on Likert scales (1 - totally disagree; 5 - totally agree). Sample items were "I often think about quitting", "I feel emotionally drained by my work", "Creativity is encouraged here", and "I work under a great deal of tension". Cronbach's alpha coefficients for each scale were 0.88, 0.87, 0.83 and 0.77 respectively.

OCB was measured by adapting a scale taken from Williams & Anderson (1991)'s study. The scale was designed to measure the two OCB dimensions, OCB-I and OCB-O. It consisted of 12 items (7 items for OCB-I and 5 items for OCB-O). Sample items were "Does the work of his/her friend who is absent", "Shares all information with colleagues" and "Does not spend time on personal matters during work". Each item was answered via a five-point Likert scale: 1 - almost never, through to 5 - almost always. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for each dimension were 0.85 for OCB-I, 0.89 for OCB-O.

Sucker effect is the counter loafing behavior towards the social loafing behaviors' of colleagues. The sucker effect was measured with a five-item scale adapted from Mulvey & Klein (1998) and Jassawalla et al. (2009). Sample items were "Because my colleagues are not contributing as much as they could, I'm not trying my best" and "Because my colleagues are putting in less effort than they are able, I do not plan to continue to work hard". The reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.71.

Identification is measured with a 6-item scale adapted from Mael & Ashforth (1992). The scale evaluates the identification as a one-dimensional construct. Each item referred to a 5-point rating scale. The reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.87.

Organizational trust is measured with a scale adapted from Searle et al. (2011). The measure comprises of 5 items and focuses on employees' perceptions of whether their organization is trustworthy with regard to its competence and goodwill. The reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.90.

Conflict with colleagues is measured with 4 items adapted from Spector & Jex (1998). It was designed to assess how well the respondent gets along with others at work. The items ask about getting into arguments with others and about how often others act nasty. Respondents were asked to indicate how often each item occurs at work. Five response choices are given, ranging from 1 (rarely) to 5 (very often). High scores represent frequent conflicts with others. Sample items were "I often get into debates with my colleagues" and "My colleagues often shout at me". The reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.90.

Job performance is tested on a 4-point self-assessment scale developed by Kirkman & Rosen (1999). The scale contains expressions such as "Achieving more than business goals" and "Providing the fastest solution when a problem arises". The reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.83.

3.3 Validity of the scales

To ensure the construct validity of the study variables, CFA was conducted with AMOS software. In CFA, maximum likelihood estimation on the covariance matrix is used. A model, in which all variables were loaded in, the separate latent factors was tested. This model produced an acceptable fit ($\chi^2 = 32.20$, $p < 0.01$; $df = 8$, goodness of fit = 0.91, comparative fit index = 0.90, root mean square error of approximation = 0.04, incremental fit index = 0.91). Thus, all of the variables were adopted as distinct constructs.

4. Findings

In order to test the validity of the CCB scale in the Turkish context, we performed a confirmatory factor analysis. The test model and beta coefficients are presented in Figure 1. Results show that all items yield significant contribution to latent variable and their impacts on CCB are almost equal. The test results of confirmatory factor analysis model are shown on Table 1. The results suggest that one-factor model of CCB is significant and produces acceptable indices.

TABLE 1. CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS RESULTS OF THE CCB SCALE

Scale/model	$\Delta\chi^2$	df	$\Delta\chi^2/df$	RMSEA	CFI	RFI	IFI	GFI
CCB (One-factor)	16,15 *	6	2.69	0.04	0.94	0.89	0.94	0.95

Note: RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; CFI = Comparative Fit Index; RFI = Relative Fit Index; IFI = Incremental Fit Index; GFI = Goodness of Fit Index * $p < 0.001$.

FIGURE 1. TEST MODEL OF CCB SCALE

Correlation analysis results are presented in Table 2. The obtained correlation findings present a significant correlation between all variables except for the relationship between compulsory citizenship behavior and innovativeness ($r = -0.07, p > 0.05$), and organization oriented organization citizenship behavior ($OCB - O$) ($r = -0.03, p > 0.05$). CCB is significantly and positively correlated with intention to leave the work, burnout, job stress, social loafing, and conflict with colleagues. CCB is significantly and negatively correlated with job performance, identification, individual oriented organizational citizenship behavior, and organizational trust.

The research performed the hierarchical regression analysis in order to test the impact of the CCB on dependent variables. Primarily, demographic variables such as level of education, age, gender and duration of employment are included in the equation in the first phase and their impact is controlled. In the second phase, the impact of CCB is examined.

Hypothesis 1 argues that there is positive correlation between CCB and intention to leave the work, burnout, job stress, social loafing behavior, and conflict between colleagues. According to the obtained findings, it has been found that CCB significantly explains 32% of the variance in intention to leave the work ($\beta = 0.56, p < 0.001$), 33% of the variance on burnout ($\beta = 0.57, p < 0.001$), 14% of the variance on job stress ($\beta = 0.37, p < 0.001$), 21% of the variance on social loafing ($\beta = 0.44, p < 0.001$), and 15% of the variance on conflict between colleagues ($\beta = 0.37, p < 0.001$). Based on these findings, Hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Hypothesis 2 tests that there is negative relationship between CCB and innovativeness, identification, OCB, and organizational trust. According to the obtained findings, it is found that CCB significantly explains 2% of the variance in innovativeness ($\beta = -0.09, p < 0.05$), 3% of the variance on identification ($\beta = -0.11, p < 0.01$), and 3% of the variance in individual oriented OCB ($\beta = -0.10, p < 0.05$); and presents no significant impact on organization oriented OCB ($\beta = -0.03, p > 0.05$) and organizational trust ($\beta = -0.05, p > 0.05$). Based on these findings, Hypothesis 2 is partly accepted.

TABLE 2. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS, RELIABILITIES, AND INTER-CORRELATIONS BETWEEN THE VARIABLES

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1.CCB	2.88	0.89	(0.91)											
2.Intention to quit	2.76	1.01	0.55**	(0.88)										
3.Burnout	2.93	0.92	0.57**	0.57**	(0.87)									
4.Innovation	3.83	0.71	-0.07	-0.20**	-0.11**	(0.83)								
5.Job stress	2.77	1.04	0.36**	0.37**	0.35**	-0.11**	(0.77)							
6.Job performance	3.91	0.73	-0.14**	-0.18**	-0.09*	0.55**	-0.16**	(.83)						
7.Identification	3.75	0.77	-0.10**	-0.16**	-0.09*	0.52**	-0.12**	0.50**	(0.87)					
8.OCB-I	3.89	0.74	-0.10**	-0.21**	-0.13**	0.51**	-0.11**	0.55**	0.51**	(0.85)				
9.OCB-O	3.67	0.66	-0.03	-0.11**	0.03	0.49**	-0.05	0.50**	0.51**	0.54**	(0.89)			
10.Sucker effect	2.55	1.02	0.41**	0.47**	0.45**	-0.14**	0.49**	-0.20**	-0.07	-0.15**	0.01	(0.71)		
11.Conflict with colleagues	2.38	1.11	0.36**	0.44**	0.36**	-0.18**	0.37**	-0.29**	-0.18**	-0.29**	-0.15**	0.52**	(0.72)	
12.Organization al trust	3.22	0.46	-0.08*	-0.16**	-0.05	0.16**	-0.09*	0.17**	0.15**	0.21**	0.14**	-0.10*	-0.09*	(0.90)

Note: N = 635; *p<.05, **p<.01. Reliability scores (Cronbach alpha) are given in parenthesis.

TABLE 3. HIERARCHICAL REGRESSION ANALYSIS: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CCB AND THE DEPENDENT VARIABLES

	Intention to leave		Burnout		Innovation		Job stress		Job performance	
	Step		Step		Step		Step		Step	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
	β		β		β		β		β	
Age	-0.01	0.06	-0.05	0.01	0.15**	0.14*	-0.10	-0.05	0.15**	0.13
Job duration	-0.07	-0.05	0.02	0.04	-0.15**	-0.15**	0.02	0.04	-0.12*	0.13*
CCB		0.56***		0.57***		-0.09*		0.37***		0.14***
R^2	0.01	0.32	0.01	0.33	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.14	0.01	0.03
Adjusted R^2	0.01	0.31	0.00	0.32	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.02
F	2.431	53.868***	2.052	55.389***	2.177	2.763*	1.049	19.055***	1.921	3.931**

Note: CCB (Compulsory Citizenship Behavior), N = 635, *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001.

TABLE 4. HIERARCHICAL REGRESSION ANALYSIS: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CCB AND THE DEPENDENT VARIABLES (CONT.)

	Identification		OCB-I		OCB-O		Sucker effect		Conflict with colleagues		Organizational trust	
	Step		Step		Step		Step		Step		Step	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
	β		β		β		β		β		β	
Age	0.15**	0.13*	0.11*	0.10	0.23***	0.22***	-0.04	0.00	-0.13*	-0.08	0.10	0.10
Job duration	-0.11**	-0.12*	-0.14*	-0.14**	-0.23***	-0.23***	-0.02	-0.01	0.03	0.04	-0.09	-0.10
CCB		-0.11**		-0.10*		-0.03		0.44***		0.37***		-0.05
R^2	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.21	0.02	0.15	0.01	0.01
Adjusted R^2	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.20	0.01	0.14	0.00	0.00
F	2.606**	3.466**	2.822	3.483**	6.076***	5.025***	2.593*	29.796***	2.959*	20.633***	1.345	1.454

Note: CCB (Compulsory Citizenship Behavior), N = 635, *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001.

When regression analysis findings are evaluated, CCB is dramatically effective in explaining negative behaviors and attitudes such as intentions to leave the work or burnout. However, even though it has negative impact on positive attitudes and behaviors such as innovativeness or identification, this impact remains limited. In this context, it can be considered that CCB would have important impact on negative organizational consequences.

5. Discussion

The findings obtained, as expected, show that CCB is positively correlated with negative organizational consequences; and negatively correlated with positive organizational attitudes and behaviors. According to this, manager/supervisor related CCBs increase employees' intentions to quit work, their level of burnout, job stress, social loafing behaviors, and conflict with their colleagues; and they decrease their innovative behaviors, identification with the organization, and individual oriented OCBs.

Although the subject of possible negative consequences of OCB in the area of management is a relatively old subject, CCB is a rather new subject. After the two fundamental articles of Vigoda-Gadot, the interest in the one has increased. However, there are no studies examining the essential dynamics of CCB in different cultures and different sectors. In this regard, this research has made contribution to the respective literature.

When the subject is evaluated in the context of Turkey, it is seen that CCB scale can be used as valid and reliable scale in the country. However, the validity and reliability of the scale should be tested with different studies conducted in different sectors and its generalizability power should be increased.

References

Bateman, T. S., & Organ, D. W. 1983. Job satisfaction and the good soldier: The relationship between affect and employee citizenship. *Academy of Management Journal*, 26(4), 587-595.

Bolino, M. C., Turnley, W. H., & Niehoff, B. P. (2004). The other side of the story: Reexamining prevailing assumptions about organizational citizenship behavior. *Human Resource Management Review*, 14(2), 229-246.

Brief, A. P., & Motowidlo, S. J. 1986. Prosocial organizational behaviors. *Academy of Management Review*, 11(4), 710-725.

Folger, R. 1993. Justice, motivation and performance beyond role requirements. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 6(3), 239-248.

- George J. M., & Brief, A. P. 1992. Feeling good-doing good: A conceptual analysis of the mood at work-organizational spontaneity relationship. *Psychological Bulletin*, 112(2), 310-329.
- Jassawalla, A., Sashittal, H., & Malshe, A. 2009. Students' perceptions of social loafing: Its antecedents and consequences in undergraduate business classroom teams. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 9(1), 42-54.
- Kidwell, R., Mossholder, K. & Benneth, N. 1997. Cohesiveness and organizational citizenship behavior. *Journal of Management*, 23(6), 775-793.
- Kirkman, B.L., & Rosen, B. 1999. Beyond self-management: Antecedents and consequences of team empowerment. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 42(1), 58-74.
- Mael, F., & Ashforth, B. 1992. Alumni and their alma mater: A partial test of the reformulated model of organizational identification. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 13(2), 103-123.
- Moorman, R. H. 1991. Relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behaviors: Do fairness perceptions influence employee citizenship? *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(6), 845-855.
- Motowidlo, S. J., & Van Scotter, J. R. 1994. Evidence that task performance should be distinguished from contextual performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 79, 475-480.
- Mulvey, P.W., & Klein, H.J. 1998. The impact of perceived loafing and collective efficacy on group goal processes and group performance. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 74(1), 62-87.
- Organ, D.W. 1988. *Organizational citizenship behavior: The good soldier syndrome*. Lexington, England: Lexington Books.
- Organ, D. W., & Ryan, K. 1995. A meta-analytic review of attitudinal and dispositional predictors of organizational citizenship behavior. *Personnel Psychology*, 48, 775-802
- Podsakoff, P. M., Ahearne, M., & Mackenzie, S. B. 1997. Organizational citizenship behavior and the quantity and quality of work group performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 82, 262-270.
- Podsakoff, P. M., Mackenzie, S. B., Paine, J. B., & Bachrach, D. G. 2000. Organizational citizenship behaviors: A critical review of the theoretical and empirical literature and suggestions for future research. *Journal of Management*, 26(3), 513-563.
- Porpora, D. V. 1989. Four concepts of social structure. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behavior*, 19(2), 195-211.
- Rioux, S. M., & Penner, L. A. 2001. The causes of organizational citizenship behavior: A motivational analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(6), 1306-1314.
- Smith, C. A., Organ, D., & Near, Y. 1983. Organizational citizenship behavior: Its nature and antecedents. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 68(4), 653-663.
- Spector, P.E., & Jex, S. M. 1998. Development of four self-report measures of job stressors and strain: Interpersonal conflict at work scale, organizational constraints scale, quantitative workload inventory, and physical symptoms inventory. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 3(4), 356-367.
- Tepper, B. J. 2000. Consequences of abusive supervision. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43(2), 178-190.
- Tepper, B. J., Duffy, M. K., Hoobler, J., & Ensley, M. D. 2004. Moderators of the relationships between coworkers' organizational citizenship behavior and fellow employees' attitudes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(3), 455-465
- Turnipseed, D., & Murkison, G. 1996. Organizational citizenship behavior an examination of influence the workplace. *Leadership and Organizational Development Journal*, 17, 42-47.
- Van Dyne, L., & Lepine, J. A. 1998. Helping and voice extra-role behaviors: Evidence of construct and predictive validity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 41, 108-119.
- Vigoda-Gadot, E. 2006. Compulsory citizenship behavior: Theorizing some dark sides of the good soldier syndrome in organizations. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behavior*, 36(1), 77-93.
- Vigoda-Gadot, E. 2007. Redrawing the boundaries of OCB? An empirical examination of compulsory extra-role behavior in the workplace. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 21(3), 377-405.
- Williams, L., & Anderson, S. 1991. Job satisfaction and organizational commitment as predictors of organizational citizenship and in role behaviors. *Journal of Management*, 17(3), 601-617.